

STUDIES ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF BI-UNIVALENT SALTS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART V. CADMIUM ACETATE

BY S. ADITYA AND B. PRASAD

The nature of cadmium acetate has been studied from the E. M. F. measurements of the cells--

The constants for the first stage of dissociation, $\text{CdAc} \rightleftharpoons \text{CdAc}^+ + \text{Ac}^-$ is 1.0×10^{-1} and that of the second stage, $\text{CdAc}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{Ac}^-$ is 1.7×10^{-2} . These have been calculated from the study of the cells 'A' and 'B' on some assumptions. The study of the cell 'C' justifies these assumptions.

Cadmium has a great tendency to co-ordination and its salts very often form auto-complexes in solution. The variation of transport number with concentration is ascribed to the formation of complexes. The behaviour of its chlorides and bromides has been studied by Riley and Gellafant (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 514).

Farrel, Ridgeon and Riley (*ibid.*, 1934, 1440) studied the reaction between cadmium ion and different carboxylic acid by means of potentiometric titration. They conclude that mostly undissociated cadmium acetate is formed. Their values of K_1 corresponding to $\text{CdAc}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdAc}^+ + \text{Ac}^-$ vary from 0.63×10^{-2} to 2×10^{-2} . They did not take interionic forces into account.

Quintin (*Compt. rend.*, 1941, 212, 855) measured the conductance of cadmium acetate and concluded that cadmium acetate was only partially dissociated. Subsequently, however, he (*J. chim. phys.*, 1942, 77, 39) ascribed the deviation rather to hydrolysis than to the association of ions.

Leden (*Svensk Kem. Tid.*, 1946, 58, 129) has reported the existence of CdAc^+ and CdAc_2^{--} ions.

In the present work the study of the following cells was undertaken to throw light on the nature of cadmium acetate in solution.

The junction potential is practically eliminated as pointed out in previous communications (*this Journal*, 1952, 29, 169 ; 1953, 30, 213, 217).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The E.M.F. of all the cells were studied in an air thermostat kept at 30°. In all the cases cadmium amalgam of the same composition, prepared as described in Part IV of this series (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 217) was used. Cadmium acetate trihydrate and cadmium nitrate (both Merck and Co., A.R.) were used. The cadmium acetate trihydrate was found to be 100% pure as tested volumetrically by oxine method. All solutions of cadmium acetate were made by direct weighing. Cadmium nitrate being hygroscopic, a stock solution was made and its concentration was estimated as above. All necessary solutions were made from this. The cell vessels and the bridge used were of the type described earlier (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 683). Each half cell of the cells I and II was prepared in duplicate. The duplicate cells were joined to each other by means of a rubber tubing containing the same solution as in the duplicate cells and the E.M.F. was measured, and if it exceeded 0.1 m.v., the half cells were discarded. Then the cells of the type I and II were set up by joining the proper half cell by means of salt bridge. The E.M.F. of these cells did not differ by more than 0.2 m.v. In every case the mean of the two was taken. The cell III was always set up in duplicate and the E.M.F. agreed within 0.1 m.v.

The E.M.F. of the cell

having the same molar concentration of cadmium nitrate and cadmium acetate but different concentration of acetic acid gave a linear plot against the concentration of acetic acid, and the values of E.M.F. corresponding to zero concentration of acetic acid as found by extrapolation are given in column 4 of Table I.

If activity coefficients are assumed to be unity and cadmium acetate dissociates as

the E.M.F. of the concentration cell $\text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y \mid \text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \parallel \text{bridge} \parallel \text{CdAc}_2, \text{HAc} \mid \text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y$ will be given by

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{2}{1 + \gamma}$$

as cadmium nitrate is completely dissociated (Part IV, *loc. cit.*). When the dissociation is calculated with this equation, the value γ becomes negative in four out of six cases (negative in concentration 0.04, 0.06, 0.08, 0.1M). Hence, this scheme is discarded.

If cadmium acetate dissociates in the following way,

the E.M.F. of the above cell will be given by the equation

$$E_1 = \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{a_{\text{Cd}^{++}} \text{ in Cd(NO}_3)_2 \text{ solution}}{c^2 \beta f_{\text{Cd}^{++}} \text{ in CdAc}_2 \text{ solution}}$$

The activity coefficient of cadmium nitrate is not found in literature. As cadmium nitrate is completely dissociated, the activity coefficient of cadmium ion ($a_{\text{Cd}^{++}}$) in cadmium nitrate may be assumed to be equal to that of barium chloroide of the same ionic strength and calculated on the lines given by Lewis ("Thermodynamics", 1923, p. 379). Knowing E_1 and $a_{\text{Cd}^{++}}$ it was possible to calculate $\alpha\beta f_{\text{Cd}^{++}}$.

On the basis of the same scheme of dissociation, the E.M.F. of the cell

extrapolated to zero concentration of acetic acid is given by

$$E_2 = \frac{RT}{F} \log \frac{a_{\text{Ac}^-} \text{ in NaAc solution}}{c\beta(1+\alpha)f_{\text{Ac}^-} \text{ in CdAc}_2 \text{ solution}}$$

The E.M.F. values of these cells are given in Table II.

The activity of acetate ion was assumed in sodium acetate to be equal to that of chloride ion in sodium chloride at the same ionic strength since both sodium chloride and sodium acetate solutions were dilute and completely dissociated and of the same valence type. So it became possible to calculate the value of a_{Ac^-} in sodium acetate solution and that of $\beta(1+\alpha)f_{\text{Ac}^-}$ in cadmium acetate solution.

The ionic strength (μ) of the cadmium acetate solutions is given by $\mu = \beta c(1 + 2\alpha)$. Assuming $f_{\text{Cd}^{++}}$ and f_{Ac^-} to be unity, a rough value of α , β and ionic strength is obtained from the values of $\alpha\beta f_{\text{Cd}^{++}}$ and $\beta(1+\alpha)f_{\text{Ac}^-}$ known earlier. From this rough value of ionic strength it is possible to find out a value of $f_{\text{Cd}^{++}}$ and f_{Ac^-} in cadmium acetate on the basis: (1) the activity coefficient of cadmium ion in cadmium acetate solution is equal to that of barium ion in barium chloride solution of the same ionic strength and (2) the activity coefficient of acetate ion is equal to that of chloride ion in the solution of the same ionic strength. The values of α , β , μ as well as $f_{\text{Cd}^{++}}$ and f_{Ac^-} are then correctly determined by the method of approximations. About three approximations are enough. The final value of α and β are given in columns 5 and 6 of Table II.

The values of K_1 and K_2 are given by the following equations,

$$K_1 = \frac{a_{\text{CdAc}^+} \times a_{\text{Ac}^-}}{a_{\text{CdAc}_2}} = \frac{(1-\alpha)\beta c(1+\alpha)\beta c f_{\text{CdAc}^+} f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{(1-\beta)c f_{\text{CdAc}_2}} = \frac{(1-\alpha^2)\beta^2 c f_{\text{CdAc}^+} f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{(1-\beta)}$$

TABLE I

Cell : $\text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y \mid \text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2(c) \parallel \text{Salt} \parallel \text{CdAc}_2(c)\text{HAc}(c_1) \mid \text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y$.
bridge

Concentration of cadmium acetate and cadmium nitrate.	Concentration of acetic acid.	R. M. F. (mean of the duplicate).	Extrapolated value of R.M.F.
0.01 M	0.005 M	0.0063	0.0064
	0.010	0.0060	
	0.015	0.0055	
	0.020	0.0054	
0.02	0.005	0.0077	0.0075
	0.010	0.0069	
	0.015	0.0068	
	0.020	0.0067	
0.04	0.005	0.0106	0.0107
	0.010	0.0104	
	0.015	0.0103	
	0.020	0.0103	
0.06	0.005	0.0114	0.0116
	0.010	0.0113	
	0.015	0.0111	
	0.020	0.01085	
0.08	0.005	0.0137	0.0142
	0.010	0.0126	
	0.015	0.0120	
	0.020	0.0115	
0.1	0.005	0.0159	0.0164
	0.010	0.0153	
	0.015	0.0148	
	0.020	0.0144	

In arriving at the last term the activity coefficient of undissociated cadmium acetate is taken to be unity. Further, the activities of monovalent CdAc^+ and Ac^- ions are taken to be equal to that of the chloride ion in solutions having the same ionic strength. The values of K_2 , thus determined, are given in column 7 of Table II and the mean value is 1×10^{-1} .

$$K_2 = \frac{a_{\text{Cd}^{++}} a_{\text{Ac}^-}}{a_{\text{CdAc}^+}} = \frac{\beta(1+\alpha)c_{\text{Ac}^-} \alpha \beta c_{\text{Cd}^{++}}}{\beta(1-\alpha)c_{\text{CdAc}^-}} = \frac{(1+\alpha)\beta c_{\text{Ac}^-} c_{\text{Cd}^{++}}}{(1-\alpha)}$$

TABLE II

Cell : Hg, Hg₂Ac₂ | CdAc₂(c) HAc(c₁) || Salt || NaAc(2c)HAc(c₁) | Hg₂Ac₂, Hg.
bridge

Conc. of CdAc ₂ .	Conc. of acetic acid.	E.M.F.	Extrapolated E.M.F.	β .	α .	K_1 .	K_2 .
0.01 M	0.005 M	0.0054	0.0054	1.00	0.6073	---	1.406 × 10 ⁻²
	0.010	0.0054					
	0.015	0.0055					
	0.020	0.0055					
0.02	0.005	0.0090	0.0090	0.915	0.5508	0.977 × 10 ⁻¹	1.717 × 10 ⁻²
	0.010	0.0089					
	0.015	0.0091					
	0.020	0.0091					
0.04	0.005	0.0127	0.0126	0.855	0.4421	0.816 × 10 ⁻¹	1.667 × 10 ⁻²
	0.010	0.0126					
	0.015	0.0128					
	0.020	0.0128					
0.06	0.005	0.0148	0.0148	0.785	0.4420	0.822 × 10 ⁻¹	2.04 × 10 ⁻²
	0.010	0.0146					
	0.015	0.0148					
	0.020	0.0148					
0.08	0.005	0.0156	0.155	0.9001	0.3473	1.300 × 10 ⁻¹	1.646 × 10 ⁻²
	0.010	0.0155					
	0.015	0.0157					
	0.020	0.0157					
0.1	0.005	0.0181	0.0180	0.7381	0.3121	1.048 × 10 ⁻¹	1.410 × 10 ⁻²
	0.010	0.0181					
	0.015	0.0182					
	0.020	0.0183					

Mean value of $K_1 = 1.0 \times 10^{-1}$.

Mean value of $K_2 = 1.7 \times 10^{-2}$.

The values of K_2 are given in column 8 of Table II and the mean is 1.7×10^{-2} .

For the cells of HgHg₂Ac₂ | CdAc₂(c)HAc(c₁) | Cd₂Hg₂ the electrode vessels were the same as used in the study of HgHg₂Ac₂ | PbAc₂ | Pb₂Hg₂ (Part III, *loc. cit.*). Here also, acetic acid was added to suppress hydrolysis. The experimental data are given in Table III. The column 4 gives the extrapolated values. The E.M.F. of this type of cell extrapolated to zero concentration of acetic acid is given by

$$E_s = E_0 - \frac{RT}{2F} \log \alpha \beta c f_{ad}^{++} (1 + \alpha)^2 \beta^2 c^2 f_{ad}^{--}.$$

TABLE III

Cell : $\text{Hg} \text{Hg}_2\text{Ac}_2 \mid \text{CdAc}_2(\text{c})\text{HAc}(\text{c}_1) \mid \text{Cd}_2\text{Hg}_2 -$

Conc of CdAc.	Conc. of acetic acid.	E.M.F. observed.	Extrapolated E.M.F.	E_0 calculated.
0.01 M	0.005 M	1.04315	1.0431	0.8574
	0.010	1.04310		
	0.015	1.04295		
	0.020	1.04310		
0.02	0.005	1.0253	1.0252	0.8582
	0.010	1.0255		
	0.015	1.0255		
	0.020	1.0255		
0.04	0.005	1.0078	1.0077	0.8576
	0.010	1.0079		
	0.015	1.0081		
	0.020	1.0082		
0.06	0.005	0.9981	0.9995	0.8581
	0.010	0.9984		
	0.015	0.9984		
	0.020	0.9982		
0.08	0.005	0.99055	0.9995	0.8569
	0.010	0.99065		
	0.015	0.9908		
	0.020	0.9916		
0.1	0.005	0.9875	0.9885	0.8568
	0.010	0.9873		
	0.015	0.9865		
	0.020	0.9860		

Mean value of $E = 0.8575$ volt.

The values of α and β , $f_{\text{Cd}^{++}}$ and f_{H^+} for the various concentrations of cadmium acetate are known from the study of the cells I and II. With the values of E_s , obtained as described above, it is possible to calculate the value of E_0 in case of each cell and the values are given in Table III. The values of E_0 do not differ from the mean by more than 0.7 m.v. This may be taken to be a justification for the assumptions regarding the elimination of liquid junction potential and the values of activity coefficients.